

VIBRATION AND ACOUSTIC PROPERTIES OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH EMBEDDED LITHIUM-ION POLYMER BATTERIES

J. Galos¹, A. Afaghi Khatibi², and A.P. Mouritz³

¹ School of Engineering, RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, VIC 3001, Australia

Email: joel.galos@rmit.edu.au, web page: www.rmit.edu.au

² School of Engineering, RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, VIC 3001, Australia

Email: akbar.afaghikhatibi@rmit.edu.au, web page: www.rmit.edu.au

³ School of Engineering, RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, VIC 3001, Australia

Email: adrian.mouritz@rmit.edu.au, web page: www.rmit.edu.au

Keywords: sandwich, vibration, acoustics, multifunctional

ABSTRACT

Composite structures containing lithium-ion polymer (LiPo) batteries are being developed for energy storage on motor vehicles and other applications. This paper presents an experimental and numerical study into the effect of embedding (LiPo) batteries into sandwich panels on the vibration and acoustic properties. The vibration responses (modal frequencies, damping) were measured experimentally using laser Doppler vibrometry and calculated numerically using finite element modal analysis. The results reveal that careful placement of LiPo batteries within composite structures is needed to control the vibration properties. Embedding batteries at the nodal points of the sandwich composite increases the vibration bending damping ratio for modes II and III, with improvements of up to 310% (mode III). LiPo batteries also improve the acoustic performance by increasing the coincidence frequency and decreasing the wavenumber amplitude at frequencies above the first vibration bending mode. The results indicate that the judicious placement of embedded LiPo batteries can improve the vibration and acoustic properties of sandwich composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is growing pressure on the global automotive industry to increase the fuel economy of automobiles and to lower the emission of greenhouse gasses and other atmospheric pollutants. One approach is to use carbon fibre-polymer sandwich composites to reduce the body weight and thereby reduce fuel burn and the resultant release of pollutants. Another approach is the replacement of the internal combustion engine with hybrid or electric engines. The automotive industry is keen to combine light-weight composite materials technology with hybrid or electric engine technology to produce environmentally friendly vehicles which are fuel efficient. However, such vehicles require much larger (and therefore heavier and bulkier) energy storage systems than conventional internal combustion vehicles, which negate some of the benefits. Despite the use of high capacity energy storage systems such as lithium-ion (LiPo) batteries, weight remains a significant challenge to their use in motor cars. One approach to overcome this problem is to lower the overall mass of hybrid and electric vehicles by integrating the LiPo batteries within the vehicle structure (e.g. body panels, chassis, door pillars) [1, 2].

The changes to the mechanical properties of composites when batteries are embedded inside the material have been determined [e.g. 3-5]. However, the effect of embedded batteries on the dynamic properties of sandwich composites has not been determined. A critical design issue in vehicle design is noise and vibration harshness (NVH), with the design objective being to minimise the acoustic noise and vibrations experienced by the occupants. In general, composites (particularly sandwich materials) can be tailored to have superior vibration damping properties compared to steel and other traditional structural materials used in motor cars. The damping properties of composites can be several orders of magnitude higher than traditional vehicle materials (depending on the vibrational frequency and mode) [6]. However, it is not known whether embedding an energy storage system will adversely affect the

vibrational properties of composites. LiPo batteries have stiffness and other mechanical properties that are much lower than the composite materials used in motor cars. It may be expected that embedded batteries for energy storage within composite automotive components will affect their NVH properties, although this has not yet been determined.

Modal analysis is a technique commonly used to assess the NVH properties of automotive components. It involves measurements of the modal frequency (absorption of energy), modal damping (dissipation of energy) and mode shapes (deflection shape at a modal frequency) of components, and the analysis compares these parameters to benchmark modal conditions.

The high specific stiffness of carbon fibre composites typically leads to good vibration damping properties that are favourable in many engineering applications. However, these properties can also cause poor acoustic performance. Sandwich composites especially can be good radiators of noise. To this end, several studies have examined the acoustic properties of sandwich panels, particularly with relation to vibration-generated noise [7, 8]. However, the effect of embedded batteries on the vibration-generated noise is not known.

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of embedding LiPo batteries into carbon fibre sandwich composites on the vibration and acoustic properties. The effect of embedding single or multiple LiPo batteries inside the sandwich composites is determined experimentally and numerically. The vibration and acoustic properties are measured experimentally using laser scanning vibrometry and predicted numerically using FE modelling. The vibration performance is quantified using the modal frequencies and damping properties whereas the acoustic performance is characterised using the coincidence frequency and wavenumber amplitude. The practical aim of this work is to determine whether internal energy storage systems using LiPo batteries will significantly alter to NVH properties of composite components.

2 MATERIALS & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite Materials and Batteries

The vibration and acoustic properties of the carbon-epoxy sandwich composite materials containing one or multiple LiPo batteries were compared against these materials without a battery. The LiPo battery used was supplied by the LiPol Battery Co. Ltd, China. Each battery was enclosed within a thin aluminium protective pouch measuring 40 mm long, 30 wide and 4 mm thick and with a weight of 10 grams. The capacity and voltage of a battery was 500 mAh and 3.7 V, respectively.

The sandwich composite material was made with 1 mm thick carbon-epoxy laminate skins and 4 mm thick polymer foam core. The total thickness of the sandwich composite was 6 mm. The skins were fabricated using plain woven T300 carbon fabric with an areal density of 200 g/m² (AC220127 supplied by Colan Ltd.) and a low-temperature cure bisphenol-A based epoxy resin (105/206 supplied by West System). The core was a 100 kg/m³ closed cell PVC foam core (Divinycell H100).

The batteries were embedded within cut-outs in the core material (Fig. 1a) prior to fabrication of the sandwich composite. The two skins each contained three plies of carbon fabric, and these were laminated directly onto the core (containing one or more batteries) using the wet hand lay-up process. The nominal cured ply thickness obtained in the wet hand layup process was 0.33 mm. The surfaces of the core and batteries were pre-wetted with the epoxy resin before lamination to promote bonding to the skins. Following fabrication, the sandwich composite was cured under ambient pressure at room temperature. The batteries were fully embedded within the core and were not part of the laminate skins (Fig. 1b). Sandwich composite beams were made without a battery, one battery or multiple batteries (up to seven) aligned in series (Fig. 2). The specimens were 400 mm long, 50 mm wide and 6 mm thick, and were used for vibration and acoustic testing.

Figure 1: Sandwich composite. (a) Top view of two batteries within cut-out sections to the foam core. (b) X-ray CT image of a cross-section view of the cured sandwich composite showing an embedded battery. Note that the white horizontal band is an artefact of the X-ray imaging and not a physical feature in the sandwich composite.

Figure 2: Schematic (top and centre section views) of the sandwich composite specimens showing the arrangement of embedded LiPo batteries. (a) One battery, (b) two batteries – 100 mm spacing, (c) three batteries – 60 mm spacing, (d) four batteries – 40 mm spacing, (e) five batteries – 30 mm spacing, (f) six batteries – 20 mm spacing, and (g) seven batteries – 10 mm spacing. All beams are symmetric about the horizontal and vertical centrelines.

2.2 Experimental vibration and acoustic analysis

The vibration and acoustic properties of the sandwich composite specimens were measured using laser scanning Doppler vibrometry, and a schematic representation of the test setup is shown in Fig. 3. A beam-shaped specimen was horizontally suspended using string at both ends from a fixed frame to provide a free-free boundary condition. A mechanical shaker was used to generate a point excitation at a fixed point 75 mm from one end of the specimen. The shaker head was bonded to the specimen using a non-permanent thermoplastic adhesive. Input force was measured using a load cell attached to the end of the shaker. A periodic chirp signal (random decrement) in the frequency range of 0 to 2.5 kHz was used to excite the specimen, with 3200 FFT lines across this bandwidth to provide a resolution of 0.78 Hz.

Figure 3: Schematic of the experimental test used in scanning laser Doppler vibrometry.

A non-contact laser vibrometer (Polytec PSV 400 with OFV-400 controller) was used to record the out-of-plane displacements, velocities and accelerations at 75 equi-distance scanning points. The distance between the scanning points was 17 mm in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. The measuring head of the Polytec system consists of a laser beam source and video camera to record images of the specimen. The head was placed at 0.7 m from the specimen to ensure a full-field of view from edge-to-edge. The controller velocity sensitivity was set to 10 mm/s/V and a 20 kHz low pass filter was used to remove high-frequency noise from the signal.

The first three modes of vibration were measured from the frequency-velocity response curves, which were obtained by averaging the responses from the 75 measurement points. The damping ratios of the specimens were also measured for the first three bending modes of vibration using the 3 dB half-power bandwidth method:

$$\zeta = \Delta\omega / 2\omega_n \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ is the difference in the frequencies which are 3 dB less than the peak. ω_n is the natural frequency for the specific vibration mode. This method is accurate for damping ratios less than 0.05. For the acoustic analysis, the coincidence frequency and wavenumber amplitude were determined for the specimens. The coincidence frequency is the frequency at which vibration becomes audible, and this was determined by analysing the LDV data in the wavenumber domain. This involves taking the frequency response function measured across the 23 equidistant points along the centre beam, and then transforming into the wavenumber domain using a Fourier transform (MATLAB). (The first and last data points along the row were omitted from the analysis as these were not equally spaced). Once transformed into the wavenumber domain, contour plots were extracted from the wavenumber-frequency response. The contours are the magnitude of normalised acceleration in wavenumber/frequency space. The peaks from the contour plots were used to identify the coincidence

frequency. The magnitude of the wavenumber correlates directly with the level of radiated noise and therefore is another important indicator of acoustic performance. The wavenumber magnitude was determined by normalising the acceleration response by input force, averaged across all 21 measurement points.

2.3 Finite Element Modelling

Numerical modal analysis was performed on the sandwich composite using 3D finite element (FE) modelling (Abaqus Version 6.14, Dassault Systemes). The models were constructed using SC8R continuum shell elements with reduced integration. A mesh convergence study was performed, and 3 mm square elements were chosen as the optimum size for numerical accuracy combined with reasonable computation times. The carbon-epoxy material was modelled as an elastic anisotropic solid whereas each embedded LiPo battery was analysed using isotropic material properties. The material properties used in finite modelling are given in Table 1. Note that the properties used for the LiPo batteries are approximations based on experimental load-displacement curves presented in [8]. The batteries were built into the FE model of the sandwich at defined locations (as shown in Fig. 2) by replacing the material properties of the elements for the polymer foam core with the properties of the LiPo battery. The battery was assumed to be perfectly bonded to the skins and core, and there were not resin-rich regions around their boundary. The two short connection points to the battery were not considered in the model.

Property	CFRP [9]	PVC foam [10]	LiPo battery [11]
ρ	1,550 kg/m ³	100 kg/m ³	2,080 kg/m ³
E_1	45.0 GPa	95.0 MPa	150 MPa
E_2	45.0 GPa	95.0 MPa	150 MPa
E_3	7.50 GPa	117 MPa	150 MPa
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	3.90 GPa	25.0 MPa	300 MPa
G_{23}	2.82 GPa	25.0 MPa	100 MPa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.32	0.3	0.3
ν_{23}	0.33	0.3	0.3

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the materials used for the FE modelling. The 1, 2 and 3 directions of the material properties are applied to the test specimens along the length, width and thickness, respectively.

The FE models were assigned free-free boundary conditions to replicate the experimental test condition. The model employed the Lanczos Eigensolver inbuilt in the Abaqus software package to extract the natural frequencies for the first three bending modes of vibration.

The FE results were compared with the experimental results through a calculation of relative difference:

$$\text{Relative difference (\%)} = ((\omega_{n,LDV} - \omega_{n,FE}) / \omega_{n,FE}) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_{n,LDV}$ and $\omega_{n,FE}$ are the values for the experimental and numerical natural frequencies, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Vibration and Damping Properties

The measured and calculated natural frequencies of the sandwich beams with and without batteries for the first three bending modes are shown in Fig. 4. The mode I frequency decreased gradually with an increasing number of batteries embedded within the sandwich material, although the changes were relatively small. For example, the reduction in the mode I frequency caused by the highest number of batteries (7) was only ~60 Hz. The frequencies for modes II and III bending vibrations did not change greatly due to the batteries. The results in Fig. 4 also show that the experimental and FE results for the first three bending modes are in good agreement, with the relative difference typically less than 10%. The FE model of the sandwich beams tended to overestimate slightly the natural frequencies for modes I and III and underestimate the frequency for mode II. The accuracy of the model for the sandwich composite could be improved with more accurate material properties for the LiPo battery. Also, the interfacial region between the battery and sandwich material was assumed in the model to be perfect, whereas in the test specimens each battery was surrounded by a resin-rich layer (Fig. 1b) which was not considered in the model. The only large difference between the measured and calculated frequency (with 25.8% relative difference) was for the mode II vibration response of the sandwich beam containing two batteries. This discrepancy is attributed to the excitation of a torsional mode of vibration rather than a pure bending mode in the experimental test. It was confirmed using the FE model that predicted a torsional mode of vibration induced by the two batteries.

Figure 4: Comparison of the natural frequencies of the sandwich composite for the first three bending modes of vibration. (a) Experimental results, (b) numerical FE results and (c) the relative difference between experimental and numerical results. Legend indicates number of embedded batteries.

The measured damping ratios for the sandwich beams with and without batteries for the first three bending modes of vibration are shown in Fig. 5. The mode I damping was reduced by the batteries, although there was no correlation between the magnitude of the reduction and the number of batteries. Regardless of their number, the batteries had a relatively minor effect of the mode II damping ratio. The mode III damping ratio was also not altered greatly by the batteries except when 6 or 7 batteries were embedded, which caused large increases. The increase in the damping ratio was caused by the localised increase in material density at the nodal points where embedded batteries were located. Fig. 6 shows the theoretical non-dimensional mode shapes for the first three bending modes for free-free vibration plotted above the non-dimensional position of embedded batteries in the sandwich composite beam. From this plot, it is evident that the specimens with increased damping ratio had batteries embedded at the theoretical nodal points. The reduction in damping ratio observed for some of the sandwich composites could be attributed to a reduction in specific shear modulus (G/ρ) of the core caused by the presence of the batteries [7]. Table 1 indicates that the specific shear modulus may be reduced significantly at the locations of embedded batteries compared to the PVC foam core.

Figure 5: Damping ratios for the sandwich composite with and without embedded batteries for the first three bending modes of vibration. Legend indicates number of embedded batteries.

Figure 6: Non-dimensional mode shapes for the first three bending modes for free-free vibration plotted above the non-dimensional position of embedded batteries.

3.2 Acoustic Properties

The coincidence frequencies for the sandwich composites determined using the dispersion plot procedure are shown in Fig. 7. This procedure is commonly used to determine the coincidence frequencies of solid sections, and the procedure is fully described in [7, 8]. The coincidence frequency was increased by the batteries, and the frequency value showed a general increase with the number of batteries. The local spike in coincidence frequency for the sandwich panel with two embedded batteries was attributed to the mode mixity of bending and torsional vibrations. This occurs when the natural frequencies of torsional and bending modes of vibration are close together. Material and structural systems with higher coincidence frequency exhibit audible structure-born noise at high frequencies and therefore have superior acoustic performance. Therefore, the results indicate that embedding LiPo batteries into sandwich composites can have a positive effect on acoustic performance in the audible frequency range.

Figure 7: Effect of number of batteries on the coincidence frequency of the sandwich composite.

The wavenumber amplitudes for the sandwich composites with or without batteries are shown in Fig. 8. The amplitude is defined as acceleration output (G-force, G) normalised by the input force measured by the transducer (in Newtons, N) during the vibration applied by the mechanical shaker. The sandwich composite shows an increase in the wavenumber amplitudes for the first bending mode of vibration. Also, the increase in wavenumber amplitude was typically greater for specimens with greater numbers of batteries. The increase in the wavenumber amplitude measured at low frequencies is attributed to the reduction in bending stiffness of the sandwich beam specimen [8]. While there was a significant increase in wavenumber amplitude for the first bending mode of vibration, this mode is below the coincidence frequency and therefore is not in the audible range. The effect of embedded batteries on the wavenumber amplitude was not as significant for higher modes of vibration. Small increases to the wavenumber amplitude were measured for the sandwich composite with one embedded battery. The wavenumber amplitudes for all other specimens remained at similar levels of magnitude or decreased. The wavenumber amplitude decreased beyond the first bending mode for the sandwich panels with six and seven batteries. This is attributed to the increase in damping ratios for these specimens, which can reduce the wavenumber amplitudes (particularly at high frequencies) [7]. This observation suggests that with careful placement of batteries within the sandwich composite structure, an improvement to the acoustic properties is possible.

Figure 8: Wavenumber domain amplitudes for the sandwich composites. Number of embedded batteries compared to control with no embedded batteries. Legends indicate number of embedded batteries.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Embedding LiPo batteries within sandwich composites for energy storage can affect the vibration and acoustic properties. Laser Doppler vibrometry experiments reveal that embedded batteries typically decrease or maintain the damping ratio of the sandwich composite. However, increases to the damping ratio can occur when batteries are embedded at locations corresponding to the theoretical vibrational nodal points. The experiments also show that embedded batteries typically cause a reduction in the modal frequency response of the sandwich composite, particularly for bending mode I. This result was confirmed numerically using finite element modal analysis.

Embedding batteries into sandwich composite materials can have a positive effect on the acoustic properties by increasing the coincidence frequency. Embedding batteries also increases the wavenumber amplitude for the first bending mode of vibration for the sandwich composite. This suggests an increase to the radiated noise should the frequency of this mode be greater than the coincidence frequency. Wavenumber amplitudes for modes beyond the first bending mode were not affected significantly by embedded batteries. Moreover, increases in damping ratio can improve the acoustic performance by increasing the coincidence frequency and decreasing the wavenumber amplitude at frequencies beyond the first bending mode of vibration.

The experimental and numerical findings reveal that careful placement of batteries within a sandwich composite structure is needed to achieve the desired vibration and acoustic performance for any given application.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was funded by the Australian Research Council (Grant Number IC160100032) as part of the ARC Training Centre in Lightweight Automotive Structures. The authors acknowledge the support of the Ford Motor Company.

REFERENCES

- [1] L.E. Asp, E.S. Greenhalgh, Structural power composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **101**, 2014, pp. 41-61.
- [2] T. Pereira, Z. Guo, S. Nieh, J. Arias, H.T. Hahn, Energy storage structural composites: a review, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **43**, 2009, pp. 549-60.
- [3] T. Pereira, Z. Guo, S. Nieh, J. Arias, H.T. Hahn, Embedding thin-film lithium energy cells in structural composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1935-41.
- [4] S. Shalouf, J. Zhang, C. Wang, Effects of mechanical deformation on electric performance of rechargeable batteries embedded in load carrying composite structures, *Plastics, Rubber and Composites*, **43**, 2014, pp. 98-104.
- [5] J.P. Thomas, M.A. Qidwai, The design and application of multifunctional structure-battery materials systems, *Journal of Materials*, **57**, 2005, pp. 18-24.
- [6] R.F. Gibson, A review of recent research on mechanics of multifunctional composite materials and structures, *Composite Structures*, **92**, 2010, pp. 2793-810.
- [7] J. Sargianis, J. Suhr, Core material effect on wave number and vibrational damping characteristics in carbon fiber sandwich composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 1493-9.
- [8] J. Sargianis, J. Suhr, Effect of core thickness on wave number and damping properties in sandwich composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 724-30.
- [9] R.B. Ladani, A.R. Ravindran, S. Wu, K. Pingkarawat, A.J. Kinloch, A.P. Mouritz, Multi-scale toughening of fibre composites using carbon nanofibres and z-pins, *Composites Science and Technology*, **131**, 2016, pp. 98-109.
- [10] I.M. Daniel, E.E. Gdoutos, Y.D.S. Rajapakse, *Major accomplishments in composite materials and sandwich structures: An anthology of ONR sponsored research*, New York, Springer, 2009.
- [11] E. Sahraei, R. Hill, T. Wierzbicki, Calibration and finite element simulation of pouch lithium-ion batteries for mechanical integrity, *Journal of Power Sources*, **201**, 2012, pp. 307-21.